

White Paper: Setting up CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) for Character Recognition

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Abstract- A Convolutional Neural Network (ConvNet / CNN) is an in-depth Learning algorithm that can take an input image, assign importance (learned weight and bias) to various aspects or objects in the image, and can be differentiated from one another. The initial processing required in a CNN is less compared to other classification algorithms. While in the initial methods the filters were engineered by hand, with adequate training, CNN was capable of knowing these filters or characteristics. The architecture of a CNN is similar to the pattern of connectivity of Neurons in the Human Brain and inspired by the organization of the Visual Cortex. Individual neurons respond only to stimuli in a restricted region of the visual field known as the Receptive Field. A collection of such fields overlap to cover the entire visual area.

Index Terms- CpnvNet or CNN(Convolutional Neural Network), Relu(Rectified Linear Unit), FC Layer(Full Connection), Val_Loss(Validation Loss), Val_Acc(Validation Accuracy)

I. INTRODUCTION

In this exercise, we will be using Keras to create the CNN. The first step of the CNN setup is to install the required libraries such as Sequential, Conv2d, Maxpooling2D, Flatten, Dense, Dropout from Keras. The coding will be carried out using the Jupyter Environment

```
[13] In [ ]:
from keras.models import Sequential
from keras.layers import Conv2D, MaxPooling2D, Flatten, Dense, Dropout
from keras.utils.np_utils import to_categorical
from keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
from PIL import ImageFile
```

Figure 1: Installation of libraries required for CNN setup.

II. CNN LAYER GENERATION

Although there are many pre-trained CNN models are available for training, the more straightforward method is programming the CNN by yourself, so that it may have the flexibility to make changes, re-configure and wider control over tuning, and training validation.

Figure 2: CNN sequence to classify handwritten digits.

Step 1: Initialization of the neural network needs to be done by creating a Sequential class object as shown in Figure 3, prior to the creation of the first layer.

Step 2: Adding the Convolutional Layer using the Convolution2D using Conv2D function with the additional parameters like.

- **Input shape:** Programmed as 40, 40, 3 (This is the three-dimensional representation batch size of the input image and includes)

- **Activation of the Relu (Rectified Linear Unit):** Without this function, the image classification will be considered as a linear problem although it's a non-linear one by the program.

Step 3: Pooling using the MaxPooling2D function: Using the general pool size of 2x2 allows reducing the feature map size while maintaining the important imagery information at the same time.

Step 4: Flattening: The pooled feature maps are required to be converted to a single vector making them into a single column.

Step 5: Creating the Full Connection (FC Layer): Using the Dense function in Keras that takes the previously created vector images. As the output dimensions in the hidden layer, for this exercise assigned 128 filter counts with the Relu activation function.

Step 6: Creating the Output Layer: As we expect more than two columns, the softmax function is used in this scenario as the activation.

After all the above configurations the CNN is required to be compiled using the Compile function that has three parameters as an optimizer, loss, and the metrics for performance. We have used the categorical “cross-entropy” function as the loss function and the ‘adam’ optimizer with ‘accuracy’ metrics.

```
[7] ▶ ▶ ML
Classifier = Sequential()
Classifier.add(Conv2D(filters = 128, kernel_size = (3,3), activation = 'relu', input_shape = (48,48,3)))
Classifier.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2,2)))
Classifier.add(Dropout(.2))

Classifier.add(Conv2D(filters = 64, kernel_size = (3,3), activation='relu'))
Classifier.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2,2)))
Classifier.add(Dropout(.2))

Classifier.add(Flatten())

Classifier.add(Dense(units = 128, activation = 'relu'))
Classifier.add(Dropout(.2))

Classifier.add(Dense(units= 53, activation = 'softmax'))

Classifier.compile(optimizer = 'adam', loss = 'categorical_crossentropy', metrics = ['accuracy'])
```

Figure 3: Coding of CNN model setup (python)

III. MODEL FITTING

The model fitting was done using the fit_generator function and using the training and test data set. The fitting was configured with 125 steps per epoch, with 80 epochs to rule out the overfitting and increased accuracy with 50 validation steps. This process was done multiple times to get the most accurate value results and to determine the most appropriate configuration. The coding and fitting results were as follows as shown in Figure 4 below.

```
[10] ▶ ▶ ML
Classifier.fit_generator(training_set, steps_per_epoch = 125, epochs = 80,
validation_data = test_set, validation_steps = 50)
125/125 [-----] - 2s 14ms/step - loss: 0.9311 - accuracy: 0.7000 - val_loss: 0.2958 - val_accuracy: 0.9300
Epoch 71/80
125/125 [-----] - 2s 14ms/step - loss: 0.8808 - accuracy: 0.7200 - val_loss: 0.1066 - val_accuracy: 0.9000
Epoch 72/80
125/125 [-----] - 2s 14ms/step - loss: 0.8580 - accuracy: 0.7400 - val_loss: 0.1721 - val_accuracy: 0.8600
Epoch 73/80
125/125 [-----] - 2s 14ms/step - loss: 0.8254 - accuracy: 0.7200 - val_loss: 0.2994 - val_accuracy: 0.9000
Epoch 74/80
125/125 [-----] - 2s 14ms/step - loss: 0.9641 - accuracy: 0.7120 - val_loss: 0.1890 - val_accuracy: 0.9500
Epoch 75/80
125/125 [-----] - 2s 14ms/step - loss: 0.7837 - accuracy: 0.7240 - val_loss: 0.2602 - val_accuracy: 0.9300
Epoch 76/80
125/125 [-----] - 2s 14ms/step - loss: 0.9164 - accuracy: 0.6960 - val_loss: 0.2348 - val_accuracy: 0.9400
Epoch 77/80
125/125 [-----] - 2s 14ms/step - loss: 0.7292 - accuracy: 0.7400 - val_loss: 0.1668 - val_accuracy: 0.9500
Epoch 78/80
125/125 [-----] - 2s 15ms/step - loss: 0.8940 - accuracy: 0.6880 - val_loss: 0.2101 - val_accuracy: 0.9500
Epoch 79/80
125/125 [-----] - 2s 15ms/step - loss: 0.8343 - accuracy: 0.7120 - val_loss: 0.1571 - val_accuracy: 0.9600
Epoch 80/80
```

Figure 4: Coding of Model Fitting.

- If **val_loss** starts increasing and **val_accuracy** starts decreasing it means the model is not learning instead it's cramming values (Tech, 2019).
- If the **val_loss** and **val_accuracy** both increase it could be due to overfitting or diverse probability values (in this case if softmax layer is used)(Tech, 2019).
- If **val_loss** is decreasing and **val_accuracy** is increasing it means the model is learning and working fine. This is the correct method we know is working (Tech, 2019).

During the process of the CNN Model training for this project, the results were more prone to indicate reducing val_loss figures while increasing val_accuracy, although it was not consistent. Therefore, during the model fitting, it was concluded that the model can be production-ready.

IV. THE CLASSIFICATION SUMMARY

The architecture of the newly created CNN model can be described as follows using Classifier.summary(), which indicates the Total parameters available, including the Trainable and Non-trainable parameters in the model.

```
[11] ▶ ▶ ML
Classifier.summary()
Model: "sequential_1"
Layer (type) Output Shape Param #
-----
conv2d_2 (Conv2D) (None, 38, 38, 128) 3584
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2 (None, 19, 19, 128) 0
dropout_3 (Dropout) (None, 19, 19, 128) 0
conv2d_3 (Conv2D) (None, 17, 17, 64) 73792
max_pooling2d_3 (MaxPooling2 (None, 8, 8, 64) 0
dropout_4 (Dropout) (None, 8, 8, 64) 0
flatten_1 (Flatten) (None, 4096) 0
dense_2 (Dense) (None, 128) 524416
dropout_5 (Dropout) (None, 128) 0
dense_3 (Dense) (None, 53) 6837
```

Figure 5: The model classifier and summary.

V. SAVING THE MODEL WEIGHTS

In the final step, the model weights were saved in both .json format and the .hdf5(.h5) formats to be used in the main script of the software solution where the user will interact to input character information. The software solution will use these model weights to replicate the recognition of the new input character information/shapes as it did in the training stage.

```
29A6q woq6J fo qI2K
bLJUF(.29A6q woq6J fo qI2K,)
CJ922I4I6L.29A6 M6I8Uf2(„2I4U9I9-CMI.µ2„)

]20U_4I46.MLJf6(CJ922I4I6L_]20U)
M4I8U ob6U(„2I4U9I9-CMI.µ20U„, „M„) 92 ]20U_4I46:

CJ922I4I6L_]20U = CJ922I4I6L.fo_]20U()
[15] ▶ ▶ ML
```

Figure 6: Saving the Model Weighted as JSON & h5 files.

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